

Review

In silico evaluation of the toxicity of sennosides and their molecular antagonists in the phytocomplex

Paolo Pelini

0000-0002-9419-6416

Profession Herbochemis Rome Italy paolo.pelini@gmail.com

Abstract:

Sennosides are molecules belonging to hydroxyanthracene derivatives (anthraquinone glucosides) present in various botanical species, in particular *Cassia Angustifolia L.* used in medicines and food supplements, for its laxative effect.

Recently, EFSA [1] published a report on the presumed genotoxicity of hydroxyanthracene derivatives (HAD) including sennosides especially if used in food supplements. In this context, new data have been collected in this work evaluating, the In Silico study of the pharmacokinetic and toxicological properties of Sennosides and the possible protective action of other molecules, in particular phytosterols present in the phytocomplex of *Cassia Angustifolia L.*, the results have shown that sennosides have a low rate of bioaccessibility, but interact with P-gp protein and Estrogen Receptor ESR1 (responsible for breast cancer). on the other hand *Cassia angustifolia L.* possesses antagonist molecules of sennosides capable of inhibiting the activation and mutation of ESR1 such as Phytosterols (stigmasterol, campesterol) and other molecules with anti-proliferative activity such as 1-monolinolene.

In this study we will focus on the inhibitory action of campesterol against ESR1 and therefore on its indirect activity as an antagonist molecule against sennosides in Senna extracts.

Introduction:

Sennosides (Sennoside A and Sennoside B) C₄₂H₃₈O₂₀ are anthraquinone glucosides naturally extracted from a plant belonging to the Cesalpiniaceae, known as *Cassia angustifolia L.* (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sennoside chemical structure in 2D and 3D (PubChem)

(<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Sennoside#section=2D-Structure>, accessed on 10 September 2024).

These molecules have been linked in 2024 by a report conducted by EFSA, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) [1] to potential adverse events of a mutagenic and carcinogenic nature.

From this study it is clear that in terms of pharmacokinetics, Sennosides show a certain bioavailability: sennosides A and B are a substrate for P-glycoprotein (P-gp) and active on the receptor for the ESR1 gene linked to breast cancer.

This study aims to provide new evidence based on computational simulations to fill some fundamental gaps regarding the toxicological and pharmacokinetic aspects of sennosides as well as to demonstrate the antagonistic action of the other molecules present in the phytocomplex, in particular the phytosterol present in *Cassia angustifolia L.* campesterol, in the possible carcinogenic contrast of sennosides in the development of tumor forms.

To achieve this goal, various bioinformatics analysis software and bibliographic searches were used that will be implemented with in vitro experiments.

Materials and methods:

In silico pharmacokinetic analysis and target prediction

The computational analysis of the pharmacokinetic and carcinogenic characteristics of Sennosides present in the phytocomplex of *Cassia Angustifolia L.* [2] was performed using the web tool SwissADME©, a free platform created and developed by the Molecular Modeling Group of the SIB, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. Based on their physicochemical characteristics, compound similarities and the provided data, the trained algorithm estimates the compounds for ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion) properties, physical chemistry, drug similarity, pharmacokinetics and medicinal chemistry properties [3]. Target prediction was performed using the SwissTargetPrediction suite [4].

In silico pharmacokinetic analysis and target prediction of sennoside derivatives

The pharmacokinetics of sennosides was verified using the SwissADME ® tools (Figure 2), which showed that these molecules have low absorption by the intestinal epithelium, but an interaction with P-gp which explains the data relating to its poor bioavailability.

For information: We have changed the look and feel of our tool. However, we have **NOT** changed the underlying technologies and parameters. Consequently, this updated Web tool provides exactly the same results as the previous version.

Enter a list of SMILES here:

OCC1OC(OC2=CC=CC3=C2C(=O)C2=C(C=C(C=C2O)C(O)=O)C3C2C3=C(C(OC4OC(C

Fill with an example | Clear | **Run!**

Show BOILED-Egg

Retrieve data: **Chemaxon** Powered by

Figure 2. Computational analysis of sennoside pharmacokinetic properties by means of SwissADME tool (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>, accessed on 10 September 2024).

Target prediction with SwissTargetPrediction (Figure 3), set as free search, without organ or signaling restrictions, confirmed that Sennosides could interact with ESR1.

SwissTargetPrediction

Target	Common name	Uniprot ID	ChEMBL ID	Target Class	Probability*	Known actives (3D/2D)
Troponin, cardiac muscle	TNNC1 TNNT2 TNNI3	P63316 P45379 P19429	CHEMBL2095202	Unclassified protein	0.71481845638	2 / 2
Estrogen receptor alpha	ESR1	P03372	CHEMBL206	Nuclear receptor	0.0642387798076	0 / 2

Figure 3. Computational analysis of sennoside prevision target by means of SwissTargetPrediction tool (http://www.swisstargetprediction.ch/result.php?job=284307115&organism=Homo_sapiens, accessed on 10 September 2024).

The interaction with the Target ESR1 makes one wonder if the single molecule and not the entire phytocomplex of *Cassia Angustifolia L.* is active and potentially carcinogenic. For this reason the author of this study wanted to investigate the anti-carcinogenic and inhibitory potential towards the Estrogen Receptor ESR1 in particular on Campesterol (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Campesterol chemical structure in 2D and 3D (PubChem) (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/173183#section=2D-Structure>, accessed on 10 September 2024).

From collected bibliographic literature [5] it is clear that this phytosterol is able to bind to the ESR1 receptor causing a conformational change resulting in its inactivation and therefore inhibiting the presumed carcinogenic action of sennosides.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the in silico research has shown that the presumed mutagenicity of sennosides as a single molecule is not directed as claimed by EFSA towards targets related to colon or intestinal cancer but possibly towards targets directed towards breast cancer, but if the entire phytochemical complex of the plant *Cassia angustifolia* L. is taken into account as it should be, this has antagonist molecules of sennosides that block and inhibit the mutagenic action towards ESR1.

The author is aware of the limitation of this work and will proceed with further in vitro experimentation on eugariotic organisms to provide further data.

References:

1. Scientific Opinion on additional scientific data related to the safety of preparations of *Rheum palmatum* L., *Rheum officinale* Baill. and their hybrids, *Rhamnus purshiana* DC., *Rhamnus frangula* L. and *Cassia senna* L., submitted pursuant to Article 8(4) of Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006
2. Determination of metabolites products by *Cassia angustifolia* and evaluate antimicrobial activity

Ali Hussein Al-Marzoqi Mohammed Yahya Hadi Imad Hadi Hameed*
Article Number - D4478E557364 Vol.8(2), pp. 25-48 , February 2016
<https://doi.org/10.5897/JPP2015.0367>
3. Daina, A.; Michielin, O.; Zoete, V. SwissADME: A Free Web Tool to Evaluate Pharmacokinetics, Drug-Likeness and Medicinal Chemistry Friendliness of Small Molecules OPEN. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 42717. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Safran, M.; Rosen, N.; Twik, M.; BarShir, R.; Stein, T.I.; Dahary, D.; Fishilevich, S.; Lancet, D. The GeneCards Suite. In *Practical Guide to Life Science Databases*; Springer: Singapore, 2022; pp. 27–56. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
5. A Virtual Drug Discovery Screening Illuminates Campesterol as a Potent Estrogen Receptor Alpha Inhibitor in Breast Cancer
June 2024 *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 67(1)
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c00766](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c00766)